

Facile fabrication of SnS and activated carbon nanocomposite for the simultaneous determination of uric acid, theophylline and caffeine

P. Kanchana, C. Sekar*

Department of Bioelectronics and Biosensors, Alagappa University, Karaikudi-630 004, TN.
Email: Sekar2025@gmail.com Mobile: +91 9442563637

Abstract

Metal sulfide nanostructures offer particular advantages to electrocatalytic performance due to their large specific surface area and easy transport of analyte. Tin sulfide (SnS), one of the important metal sulfides possess orthorhombic layered crystal structure and have a direct bandgap of about 1.32-1.5 eV, has been extensively used for electrocatalyst, lithium ion batteries, dye-sensitized solar cells *etc.* due to their high electronic conduction, low cost, nontoxicity, easy of production and storage (1). In recent years, metal sulfide-carbon composite materials have attracted a great deal of attention due to their improved electrocatalytic properties. Here, we have adopted an attractive strategy to develop SnS/activated carbon (SnS/AC) composite nanostructures, where the carbon system ensures improved electrical contact between SnS nanoparticles.

Novel activated carbon (AC) materials were prepared from the ridge gourd luffa (*Luffa acutangula*) by an eco-friendly method. Tin sulfide -activated carbon composite (SnS/AC) was synthesized by a facile one-step hydrothermal approach. The prepared nanocomposite was characterized by XRD, FTIR, FE-SEM and Raman spectroscopy. Further, the SnS/AC composite has been used for the electrochemical simultaneous determination of uric acid (UA), theophylline (TP) and caffeine (CAF). The SnS/AC modified GCE showed an excellent electrocatalytic activity for resolving the overlapping voltammetric responses of UA, TP and CAF into three well-defined voltammetric peaks. The fabricated sensor responded to UA, TP and CAF over a wide concentration range with lowest detection limit. It has an excellent anti-interference ability against electroactive species and metal ions and proved to be useful to estimate UA, TP and CAF content in the urine and energy drinks with satisfactory recovery.

Keywords: SnS, Activated carbon, uric acid, theophylline and caffeine, biosensors.

Reference

Bing Zhao et al, ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 9 (2017) 1407-1415.
